

Assessing Patient Satisfaction with Obstetrics and Gynaecology Outpatient Department at Katihar Medical College and Hospital, Katihar

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Abstract

Background: Patient's satisfaction is of utmost importance as a parameter of the quality of health care. Aim of the study is to assess satisfaction with the available services obtained from patients who were seen in outpatient department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted using questionnaires among patients attending outpatient department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India. The data were collected prospectively between 2nd March and 1st July 2022. After obtaining the consent of the individual, they were asked to complete a set of questionnaires immediately or face to face interview was done in cases where the patient was illiterate. The study instrument was a questionnaire which comprised of two parts. The first part related to respondent's socio-demographic background and second part on patient satisfaction questions.

Result: Majority of the respondents (70.0%) visited obstetrics unit while 30.0% of them visited gynaecology unit. 250 (62.5%) appointments were first attendance while rest were follow-up visits. The average patient overall satisfaction was 90.0 % in this study.

Conclusion: Overall, the patients were satisfied with services of outpatient department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India. Majority of the patients were satisfied with clinic facility, staff's professionalism, healthcare provider's attitude and quality of medical care.

Keywords: Outpatient, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Katihar, Patient Satisfaction, Medical Services.

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Introduction

Patient satisfaction is of growing importance and is profoundly recognized as an important indicator of quality of the medical care. There was no homogeneous definition of patient satisfaction, since satisfaction concerns different aspects of care or settings, as well as care given by

various professions [1]. Also, it will know that client satisfaction is of fundamental importance as a measure of the quality of care because it gives information on the provider's success in meeting client values and expectations, matters on which the client is the ultimate authority [2]. In the

current health care setting patient satisfaction is one of the main indicators. Assessment of patient satisfaction is a useful parameter to predict the quality and availability of health care services [3]. Satisfaction is, therefore, an important tool for research, administration and planning.

Nowadays, the health care sector is doing continuous efforts to ensure a higher consumer satisfaction. By doing so, one can identify the deficiencies in the delivery of healthcare services and intervene them to enhance patient satisfaction [4]. It is hard to identify a single factor that is directly associated with a low or high level of patient satisfaction.

A variety of factors might be involved in patient satisfaction process. Some of these are patient demographics, health status, characteristics of the health care provider such as technical expertise, interest in patient-oriented care and waiting time [4,5,6]. The degree of patient satisfaction with waiting times for and at gynecology outpatient clinics is a little studied area. Satisfaction is an important factor in predicting the quality of health care services provided to patients who visited gynecology and obstetrics clinics [7,8].

Patient satisfaction in general was studied in different parts of the countries, but satisfaction of patients who visited gynecology and obstetrics outdoor and its predictors were not reported in teaching hospitals in Katihar Medical College, Katihar. Results of the study may be suggested to improve the satisfaction and subsequently the quality of care of gynecology and obstetrics outdoor. Aim of the study is to assess satisfaction with services was in outpatient department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India.

Methods

A cross-sectional survey was conducted using questionnaires among patients attending outpatient department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar

Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India. The data were collected prospectively between 2nd March and 1st July 2022.

After obtaining the consent of the individual, patients were informed regarding the nature of the study and the questionnaires were distributed to the patients or face to face interview was carried out if the patient was illiterate, while they were waiting for doctors to see or after they have seen their doctors. The questionnaires were completed at waiting area of the outdoor and took an average of ten minutes to complete. The completed questionnaires were retrieved immediately. In cases, where, face to face interview were carried out then, the author of the article filled the responses in the questionnaire as per the reply of the patient.

The study instrument was a questionnaire which comprised of two parts. The questionnaire was prepared and modified according to local environment from related literature and previous studies done in the past [9,10]. The first part of the questionnaire included five items, on patient demographic variables such age, occupation, marital status, house income and education level. The second part included 28 items about service quality of the obstetrics and gynaecology clinic services: appointment system (seven items), clinic facility (four items), staff's professionalism (four items), the communication (three items), your visit with health care providers (seven items) and patient's overall satisfaction (three items). There was one additional question whether the respondents would recommend the outdoor or not. The respondents were asked reasons if they were not satisfied with any services they have received. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS program. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the study populations. Frequency and percentage were used to report proportion of the patient's satisfaction.

Results

Total 400 patients agreed to participate and completed the questionnaire at outdoor of obstetrics and gynaecology department. The mean age of the 317 respondents was 26.48 years, and ranged from 17 to 86 years. There were 200 (50%) between 17-26 years, 60 (15%) between 37-46 years, 120 (30%) between 27-36 years, 20 (05%) more than 47 years old respondents. In the study the majority of them, 340 (85%) were married and 60 (15%) were single. With regards income level, 20 (05%) of the respondents have medium income, 80 (20%) of them have high income while 300 (75%) of them have low income.

In terms of the occupation, majority of the patients were housewife [360 (90%)] while only 40 (10%) respondents belonged to working class. Majority of the respondents 200 (50%) were illiterate, 20 (05%) have graduated from primary school, 100 (25%) of them had finished high school and 80 (20%) of the respondents graduated from university. None of the candidate completed her postgraduate degree in our study (Table 1).

Majority of the respondents (70.0 %) visited obstetrics unit while only 30.0 % of them visited gynecology unit. 250 (62.5%) appointments were first attendance while rest were follow-up visits. Out of 400 respondents, 280 (70%) of them were satisfied with the system. The reasons those who were not satisfied with the appointment system related to reaching the appointment officer via phone due to the

officers were engaged with others and appointment was not available within a reasonable amount of time or due to heavy footfall at the outdoor.

The majority of the respondents (85%) were satisfied with outdoor facility while 15 % of them were not satisfied with outdoor facilities, reason ascertained were absence of water cooler and limited number of seats in the waiting area. Out of 400 respondents; 360 (90%) were satisfied with professional attitude of the health care worker while 10% of the candidates were not satisfied, reason ascertained to this was limited number of consultants in the outdoor as well as the time spent with each patient was not adequate as per them. More than half of the respondents (55%) were satisfied with communication services such as answering the patient's call promptly, helping and advising the patients regarding any query at outdoor while 45% of them were not satisfied, no reason per se was told by the respondents regarding the same. 75% of the respondents were satisfied with health care providers during their visit while 25 % of them were not satisfied, reason ascertained regarding the same was that the doctor did not have adequate time to the patient and counselled them properly regarding the status of mother and baby. 360 (90%) of the respondents were overall satisfied while 10 % of them were not satisfied due to multiple reasons like absence of water cooler, limited number of seats and consultants in the outdoor (Table 2).

Table 1: Socio-demographic profiles of respondents (n=400)

Age Group (yrs)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
17- 26	200	50
27- 36	120	30
37- 46	60	15
47 and above	20	05
Marital Status		
Married	340	85
Single	60	15
Income Level		
High	80	20
Medium	20	05
Low	300	75

Occupation		
Housewife	360	90
Working	40	10
Education Level		
Illiterate	200	50
Primary School	20	05
High School	100	25
Undergraduate	80	20
Postgraduate	00	00

Table 2: Patient satisfaction by items (n=400).

Items	Satisfied		Unsatisfied	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Appointment	280	70	120	30
Outdoor Facility	340	85	60	15
Professional attitude of staff	360	90	40	10
Communication	220	55	180	45
Visit with healthcare provider	300	75	100	25
Overall satisfaction	360	90	40	10

Discussion

The present study was carried out among 400 patients who visited outdoor department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Katihar Medical College, Katihar, Bihar, India during the study period. Majority of the respondents (90.0%) were satisfied with services they have received from the obstetrics and gynaecology outdoor. The satisfaction was higher than many studies done in the past [11,12,13]. More than half of the respondents were satisfied with appointments system but around 30 % of the respondents were not satisfied with it. The respondents who were not satisfied with appointment system may be due to their impatience or lack of literacy or they may not be familiar to the appointment system and also it could be due to patient's age, elderly may have difficulty to make appointment. The findings are similar to the study done in the past by Pandit and Mackenzie [6].

The present study found that satisfaction with professional attitude of health care workers was 90 %. This finding corroborate with the findings of study by Egan and Dowling [14] who reported that over 89% of patients were satisfied with staff in the unit. The patient's satisfaction with health

providers when they visit was 75 % which is lower in comparison to the study where 92.7% of respondents declared that they were satisfied with outpatient service providers [14]. This might be due to the fact that our institute is remotely located and it is very difficult to make patient understand their exact medical condition in such time constraint situation. Overall satisfaction was 90% of respondents in current study which was higher than 71.2% reported to have got all ordered services from the hospital [15].

Conclusion

Generally, the patients were satisfied with outdoor services of obstetrics and gynaecology department. The average overall patient's satisfaction was 90%. The patient's satisfaction with communication skills such as answered patients call promptly, giving advices and helping during office hours and with appointment system was lower compare to services. Majority of the patients were satisfied with clinic facilities, professional attitude of health care worker, healthcare provider's attitude and quality of medical care. The respondents who were not satisfied have their own reasons why they were not satisfied. The reasons are they could not

reach appointment officer immediately via phone and they were not given appropriate amount of time for their visit. The healthcare providers treated them based on their income level and they did not explain the mother's and baby's health status properly. The numbers of specialist doctors were not enough and the ultrasound machine was very limited due to these reasons they patients had to wait for long time.

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